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THE MEDIBEES PROJECT: GENETICS, PRODUCTION AND RESILIENCE
TO CLIMATE CHANGE OF THE MEDITERRANEAN
HONEY BEE SUBSPECIES

*Il progetto MEDIBEES: genetica, produzione e resilienza
al cambio climatico delle sottospecie mediterranee di ape mellifera*

Western honey bee colonies (*Apis mellifera* Linnaeus, 1758) have been kept for thousands of years to obtain honey and other direct products. Nonetheless, these last ones represent a minor part of the economic benefit coming from the presence of these insects. As pollinators, the bees perform a pivotal role both in natural – and agroecosystems. Indeed, most flowering plants depend on the presence of bees. This makes those insects considered the third most economically important animal in Europe (TAUTZ, 2008) and crucial for global food production (LEONHARDT *et al.*, 2013)].

Despite the importance of other pollinating animals, it must be recognized that honey bees have a distinct role. They are generalist pollinators, easy to keep, present in many environments, and active for long periods of the year. These insects represent hence a heritage deserving protection by suitable research initiatives also.

Honey bees have a quasi-global distribution. However, being native to the Old World, their natural populations come from Asia, Africa, and Europe. The different environments have shaped the species into at least four phylogenetic lines (A, O, M, and C) and over thirty recognized subspecies, approximately 40% of which are distributed in Mediterranean countries (MENDES FERREIRA, 2017). That makes the region a biodiversity hotspot for this species. Nonetheless, some Mediterranean beekeepers show a tendency to breed bee strains from central and northern Europe. Indeed, those bees

often show less pronounced defensive behavior than the local strains, but also imply the risk of reduced adaptation to both the local environment and plant phenology.

Global warming is forcing beekeeping to change. We need to improve our understanding of the mechanisms underlying the environmental adaptation of the various honey bee subspecies. That helps promote both keeping local strains in the areas of origin and adapting the apiculture industry to the conditions occurring under a climate change context.

The above was the basis to develop the MEDIBEES project (“Monitoring the Mediterranean honey bee subspecies and their resilience to climate change for the improvement of sustainable agro-ecosystems”), which is funded by the EU through the PRIMA Foundation. The project includes nine partners from eight countries (Algeria, Italy, Jordan, Lebanon, Malta, Portugal, Spain, and Turkey). The area covered by those countries matches the distribution area of at least ten *A. mellifera* subspecies (*A.m. anatoliaca*, *A.m. caucasica*, *A.m. iberiensis*, *A.m. intermissa*, *A.m. ligustica*, *A.m. meda*, *A.m. ruttneri*, *A.m. sabariensis*, *A.m. siciliana*, and *A.m. syriaca*).

In the four years of activity, MEDIBEES will develop the knowledge needed to unravel the genetic background of those subspecies, describe their adaptation to the specific Mediterranean conditions, and understand the mechanisms of their resilience to climate change. After a study on the characteristics of the Mediterranean beekeeping industry (WP1), testing apiaries will be established in each participating country and bee samples taken (WP2) to feed the genetic studies (WP4) needed to identify the traits of interest for future selection programmes (WP5). The knowledge achieved with those studies will be complemented with laboratory experiments assessing the effect of climate-related stressors on bee survival, reproduction, and resistance to pathogens (WP3). Besides, measures will be taken for the promotion of the honey produced in the participating countries (WP6) and the valorisation of beekeeping by-products that are normally treated as wastes (WP7). The MEDIBEES consortium is committed to an uninterrupted activity of dissemination to the beekeepers and scientific communication (WP8) and is constantly supervised by a coordination team (WP9).

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